

PREDICTING FATIGUE LIFE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Predicting fatigue life of composites is a challenge due to their anisotropic material behaviour. This paper suggested a fatigue model considering the effect of loading frequency, applied stress level, minimum-to-maximum stress ratio, fibre orientations and material properties. The model has been validated with the wide range of experimental data. Results indicated that the model can predict the fatigue life reliably if only three sets of experimental data are given to determine the material constant. This study recommended to test the specimen at 40%, 60% and 80% of the ultimate strength to determine the material constant. The suggested model is not only applicable for laminated composites but also suitable for other materials to determine their fatigue life.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are widely used in aerospace, automotive and civil construction because of their high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent durability and environmental sustainability [1-7]. Some of the structural components of these applications are subjected to cyclic loading that causes damage and material property degradation in a cumulative manner. It is important to evaluate the fatigue performance of the structure beforehand so that the maintenance or replacement of the components can be scheduled before catastrophic failure. Experimental characterisation of fatigue life for composite materials is time consuming and expensive. A reliable fatigue model can solve this problem.

Shokrieh et al. [8] outlines a progressive fatigue damage model to simulate the fatigue behaviour of composite laminates. This model consist of stress analysis, failure analysis and material property degradation rules which can be used to evaluate the state of damage at any load level and number of cycles. Their model can determine residual strength, residual life, final failure mechanisms and fatigue life of composite laminates. However, this model required many experimental data for full material characterisation. The model proposed by D'Amore et al. [9] required less number of experimental data for determining material constant. However, their model cannot explain how the loading frequency and fibre orientation affects the fatigue life of composite materials. Quaresimin et al. [10] predicted the fatigue life using multiaxial fatigue criteria. Their model showed relatively low accuracy which is unsafe in predicting fatigue life. Unfortunately, the existing fatigue models can only meet some but not all the criteria. Therefore, a reliable model for predicting fatigue life is deemed necessary.

This paper suggested a fatigue model for laminated composites to overcome the current challenges and reliable prediction of fatigue life. The glass/vinyl-ester composite samples were tested at different stress levels and the experimental data for other composites were obtained from the published literature. The model was then validated with wide range of experimental data. The outcome of this study will benefit design engineers for reliable prediction of fatigue life.

2 FATIGUE MODEL

In this study, a fatigue life model based on S-N curves is used to predict the number of cycles to failure occurring under cyclic loading conditions. Damages accumulation is not taken into account. Moreover, it is assumed that the temperature of the specimen is constant and the static ultimate strength is obtained at the same strain rate as the specimen subjected to the cyclic loading. The residual strength after constant amplitude fatigue cycles or time is related to the initial static strength as suggested by Sendeckyj [11]. Therefore,

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = -Ct^{-m} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1) σ is the residual strength after time t ; C and m are the material constants. The material constant C is the function of stress ratio (R), maximum applied stress (σ_{max}) and ultimate tensile strength (σ_u) that can be expressed by Eq. (2) where the constant A depends on the temperature of the sample, moisture content, loading type and material properties.

$$C = A.F(R, \sigma_u, \sigma_{max}) \quad (2)$$

For tension-tension loading condition, Sendekyj [11], and Hertzberg and Manson [12] formulated the effect of R , σ_u and σ_{max} on the fatigue life of GFRP composites as expressed in Eq. (3).

$$F(R, \sigma_u, \sigma_{max}) = \sigma_u^{1-\gamma} \sigma_{max}^{\gamma} (1 - \psi)^{\gamma} \quad (3)$$

The magnitude of constant γ , ($\gamma = 1.6 - \psi \sin \theta$) is in the range of $0.6 < \gamma < 7.6$ as experimentally determined by Hertzberg and Manson [12] and $\psi = R$ for tension-tension and reverse loading condition. The angle θ represents the orientation of fibre from the loading direction. The number of cycles required to degrade the strength of the material from σ_u to σ_{max} is the fatigue life which can be determined by integrating Eq. (1) from the beginning to the failure i.e., $t = t_0$ to $t = T$ as presented in Eq. (4). The time (t) is the function of number of cycles (n) and frequency (f) as specified in Eq. (5).

$$[\sigma]_{\sigma_u}^{\sigma_{max}} = -\frac{C}{-m+1} [t^{-m+1}]_{t=t_0}^{t=T, n=N} \quad (4)$$

$$t = \frac{n}{f} \quad (5)$$

Substituting Eq. (2), Eq. (3) and Eq. (5) in Eq. (4), the following relationship can be obtained

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_u}{\sigma_{max}} - 1\right) \left(\frac{\sigma_u}{\sigma_{max}}\right)^{\gamma-1} \frac{1}{(1-R)^{\gamma}} = \alpha(N^{\beta} - 1)f^{-\beta} \quad (6)$$

Where, $\alpha = \frac{A}{-m+1}$ and $\beta = -m + 1$,

Rearranging Eq. (6), the fatigue life (N) can be determined using Eq. (7).

$$N = \left[1 + \frac{f^{\beta}}{\alpha} \left(\frac{\sigma_u}{\sigma_{max}} - 1\right) \left(\frac{\sigma_u}{\sigma_{max}}\right)^{\gamma-1} \frac{1}{(1-R)^{\gamma}} \right]^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \quad (7)$$

The parameters α and β can be determined from three sets of experimental data. When plotting the left hand side of Eq. (6) against the quantity $(N^{\beta} - 1)f^{-\beta}$, it will provide a straight line passing through origin after several trials of β value where the slope of the straight line is the value of α .

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

3.1 Materials and Method

The laminated composite composed of glass fibre reinforcements and vinyl ester resin called as glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP). The fibres were oriented in longitudinal and diagonal directions with a fibre volume fraction of 55%. The nominal dimensions of the specimen was 300 mm \times 25 mm \times 5 mm including 50 mm tabs glued at both ends and tested in tension-tension loading condition.

3.2 Test Setup

The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and stiffness of the specimen were determined by the static tensile test. Fatigue tests were performed in tension-tension at an applied stress between 0.40 – 0.80 UTS, an interval of 10% and frequency of 2 Hz. The ratio of minimum-to-maximum applied stresses in a cycle called as stress ratio (R) were constant to 0.10. All tests were carried out in the load control mode with a sinusoidal waveform of constant amplitude.

4 MODEL VALIDATION

The fatigue model has been suggested with the aim of capturing the fatigue behaviour for all types of materials. The present study experimentally investigated the fatigue behaviour of GFRP composites and verified the model with the experimental data. The fatigue data for other materials were extracted from the published literature to verify the model for wide range of materials.

4.1 Triaxial Glass/Vinyl-ester Composites

The effect of applied stress level on the fatigue life (S-N curve) is plotted in Fig. 1(a). The ultimate tensile strength and elastic modulus in longitudinal direction of GFRP laminates were 500 MPa and 18 GPa, respectively. The failure modes of the specimens are shown in Fig. 1(b). The specimens at 80% and 70% of UTS were failed in tensile fracture of the fibres while the failure was due to stress concentration at 60%, 50% and 40% of the UTS. Fatigue life and loss of stiffness are increasing with the decrease of the applied stress level (Table 1).

Fig. 1: Model validation for GFRP composites

Stress (% UTS)	Fatigue life (Cycles)	Stiffness loss (%)	Failure mode
80	360	3.74	Pure tension
70	984	5.77	Pure tension
60	1879	6.04	Stress concentration
50	29174	6.84	Stress concentration
40	187292	7.45	Stress concentration

Table 1: Fatigue test results for GFRP composites

4.2 Neat Epoxy and Glass/Epoxy Composites

Manjunatha et al. [13] investigated the tensile fatigue behaviour of neat epoxy and glass/epoxy laminated composites. The epoxy resin was a standard diglycidyl ether of bis-phenol A (DGEBA) with an epoxide equivalent weight (EEW) of 185 g/eq. The resin mixture was poured into a release coated steel mold to manufacture the bulk epoxy sheets. The curing temperature was ramped to 100°C at 1°C/min for 2 hrs, again ramped to 150°C at 1°C/min and then post-cured for 10 hrs. The final thickness of the cured epoxy resin was 5 mm.

The E-glass fiber cloth was a non-crimp-fabric (NCF) roll with two layers of fiber arranged in a $\pm 45^\circ$ pattern with an areal weight of 450 g/m². The fibres were oriented in composites in a quasi-isotropic sequence of $[(+45/-45/0/90)_s]_2$ and the composites were manufactured using resin infusion process. Once completed the infusion process, the specimens were cured for 2 hrs with an increase of temperature from normal to 100°C at a rate of 1°C/min. The temperature was raised again at 1°C/min to 150°C and finally post-cured for 10 hrs. The final GFRP composite laminates were about 2.5-2.8 mm thick with a fiber volume fraction of 57%. The tensile fatigue tests was conducted at a stress ratio of 0.1 and a frequency of 1 Hz for both neat resin (10 mm wide and 5 mm thick at the middle with a length of 165 mm) and GFRP composites (25 mm wide and 150 mm long).

4.3 Carbon/Epoxy and Basalt/Epoxy Composites

Wu et al. [14] studied the tensile fatigue behaviour of carbon/epoxy and basalt/epoxy composite laminates. The unidirectional fibre fabrics of carbon and basalt were impregnated with an epoxy resin. The tensile strength and elastic modulus of epoxy resin were 51.9 MPa and 3.43 GPa, respectively. The nominal volumetric fraction of the epoxy resin was 50%. The composites were cured at room temperature for a minimum of one week prior to testing. Tapered GFRP tabs were bonded at both ends of the FRP coupons (12.5 mm wide and 250 mm long) to minimise stress concentrations near the gripping zone. The ratio of the minimum-to-maximum load was 0.1 and the loading frequency was 5 Hz.

4.4 Discussion

The suggested fatigue model accounted the effect of loading frequency (f), level of applied stress (σ_{max}/σ_u), ratio of minimum-to-maximum stress (R), fibre orientations (γ) and material properties (α and β). The model proposed by D'Amore et al. [9] considered the effect of applied stress level, minimum-to-maximum stress ratio and material properties, however, they ignored the effect of loading frequency and fibre orientations that has significant influence on fatigue life of composites. In both models, only three sets of experimental data are required to determine the material constant (α and β) as given in Table 2 for the current study. Regardless of material types, the theoretical model well captured the experimental behaviour and predicted fatigue life for glass/vinyl-ester, neat epoxy and glass/epoxy composites as shown in Figs. 1(a), 2(a) and 2(b), respectively. However, the carbon/epoxy (Fig. 2c) and basalt/epoxy (Fig. 2d) showed relatively wider variation between experimental and theoretical results. This is due to the variation of experimental results among the replica samples which is common for composite materials in order to their anisotropic nature.

The model provided the best result when there was a wide range of experimental data. The level of applied stress were varied from 40% to 80% in glass/vinyl-ester (Fig. 1a), 34 – 55% for neat epoxy (Fig. 2a) and 33 – 69% for glass/epoxy composites (Fig. 2b). The fatigue model well captured the behaviour for these three specimens. On the other hand, the prediction of fatigue life could be less reliable at low stress level as the experimental data were varied from 82% to 90% for carbon/epoxy (Fig. 2c) and 70 – 93% for basalt/epoxy composites (Fig. 2d). To achieve the reliable results from the suggested fatigue model, it is therefore recommended to determine the experimental fatigue life at a load level of 40%, 60% and 80% of the ultimate strength.

Fig. 2: Model validation for other composites

Composites	Stress ratio R	Frequency f	Material constant		
			α	β	γ
Triaxial glass/vinyl-ester	0.1	2	0.1611	0.2589	1.57
Neat epoxy	0.1	1	0.3383	0.2608	1.60
Triaxial glass/epoxy	0.1	1	0.2493	0.2482	1.58
Carbon/epoxy	0.1	5	0.1910	0.0650	1.60
Basalt/epoxy	0.1	5	0.0595	0.2014	1.60

Table 2: Test configurations and material constant

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study suggested a fatigue life prediction model and validated it through experimental data for different composite materials. The experimental program was conducted for glass/vinyl-ester composites and a wide range of data was collected from literature for neat epoxy, glass/epoxy, carbon/epoxy and basalt/epoxy composites from which the following conclusions are drawn:

- The suggested fatigue model is based on the loading frequency, applied stress level, minimum-to-maximum stress ratio, fibre orientations and material properties which accounted more parameters than the existing fatigue model.

- Only three sets of experimental data are required to determine the material constant α and β . It is recommended to obtain the experimental fatigue life at 40%, 60% and 80% of the ultimate strength to determine the material constants.
- Composite materials can provide high variations in fatigue life due to their anisotropic nature even without any variation in material and test configuration. The suggested model can predict the fatigue life for any types of material including laminated composites.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Manalo, T. Aravinthan, A. Fam, and B. Benmokrane, "State-of-the-art review on FRP sandwich systems for lightweight civil infrastructure," *Journal of Composites for Construction*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 1-16, 2016.
- [2] W. Ferdous, A. Manalo, G. Van Erp, T. Aravinthan, and K. Ghabraie, "Evaluation of an innovative composite railway sleeper for a narrow-gauge track under static load," *Journal of Composites for Construction*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 1-13, 2018.
- [3] W. Ferdous, Y. Bai, A. D. Almutairi, S. Satasivam, and J. Jeske, "Modular assembly of water-retaining walls using GFRP hollow profiles: Components and connection performance," *Composite Structures*, vol. 194, pp. 1-11, 2018.
- [4] W. Ferdous, A. D. Almutairi, Y. Huang, and Y. Bai, "Short-term flexural behaviour of concrete filled pultruded GFRP cellular and tubular sections with pin-eye connections for modular retaining wall construction," *Composite Structures*, vol. 206, pp. 1-10, 2018.
- [5] W. Ferdous, T. D. Ngo, K. T. Q. Nguyen, A. Ghazlan, P. Mendis, and A. Manalo, "Effect of fire-retardant ceram powder on the properties of phenolic-based GFRP composites," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 155, pp. 414-424, 2018.
- [6] W. Ferdous, A. Manalo, T. Aravinthan, and A. Fam, "Flexural and shear behaviour of layered sandwich beams," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 173, pp. 429-442, 2018.
- [7] W. Ferdous, Y. Bai, T. D. Ngo, A. Manalo, and P. Mendis, "New advancements, challenges and opportunities of multi-storey modular buildings – A state-of-the-art review," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 183, pp. 883-893, 2019.
- [8] M. M. Shokrieh and L. B. Lessard, "Progressive fatigue damage modeling of composite materials, Part I: Modeling," *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 34, no. 13, pp. 1056-1080, 2000.
- [9] A. D'Amore, G. Caprino, P. Stupak, J. Zhou, and L. Nicolais, "Effect of stress ratio on the flexural fatigue behavior of continuous strand mat reinforced plastics," *Science and Engineering of Composite Materials*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1-8, 1996.
- [10] M. Quaresimin, L. Susmel, and R. Talreja, "Fatigue behaviour and life assessment of composite laminates under multiaxial loadings," *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 2-16, 2010.
- [11] G. P. Sendeckyj, "Chapter 10 - Life Prediction for Resin-Matrix Composite Materials," in *Composite Materials Series*, vol. 4, 1991, pp. 431-483.
- [12] R. W. Hertzberg and J. A. Manson, *Fatigue of engineering plastics*. Academic Press, 1980.
- [13] C. M. Manjunatha, A. C. Taylor, A. J. Kinloch, and S. Sprenger, "The tensile fatigue behavior of a GFRP composite with rubber particle modified epoxy matrix," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 29, no. 14, pp. 2170-2183, 2010.
- [14] Z. Wu, X. Wang, K. Iwashita, T. Sasaki, and Y. Hamaguchi, "Tensile fatigue behaviour of FRP and hybrid FRP sheets," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 41, no. 5, pp. 396-402, 2010.